

Knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19 of employees and higher education students of St. Dominic College of Asia: A post ECQ web-based survey

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Abstract

In order to stop the COVID-19 pandemic's rapid spread, which is a global health and social emergency, thus far unheard-of actions must be taken. People's understanding, attitudes, and behaviors regarding the illness have an impact on how closely they follow control measures. Thus, the purpose of this study was to ascertain the employees' and students' level of awareness, attitudes, and practices about the COVID-19 epidemic at St. Dominic College of Asia. An online survey was conducted to determine the level of knowledge, attitude, and practices towards COVID-19 of the employees and higher education students of St. Dominic College of Asia. The responses of the respondents were described using frequencies and percentages, and the t-test was employed to identify any significant differences between the employers' and students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices. The level of knowledge towards COVID-19 is high at 82.08% for the employees and students have high level of knowledge with 77.33%. The respondents have an overall positive attitude (Employees=73.61%, Students=73.04%) in general but a less positive view on how the government is handling the pandemic (Employees=22.22%, Students=13.72%). The respondents are also implementing good practices to prevent the spread of the virus (Employees=98.15%, Students=89.87%). Hypotheses testing showed no significant difference between the employees and students' level of knowledge and attitude towards COVID-19. However, there is a significant difference in the practices of the employees and students. This means employees have much better practices on health protocols than the students.

Keywords: Knowledge; attitudes; practices; COVID-19; employees; higher education students.

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Introduction

A novel coronavirus, also known as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), is the source of the condition known as coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). It can spread quickly through personal contact with an infected person and is characterized by fast transmission. Information on the illness is always changing. Therefore, it is possible that there are other transmissions going on as well. COVID-19 has been rapidly and extensively spreading from Wuhan, China, to other nations, endangering the lives of numerous individuals. To halt its rapid spread, the World Health Organization (WHO) designated it a public health emergency of global concern in January 2020 and requested coordination from each nation. Afterwards, COVID-19 becomes a “global pandemic” according to the WHO (Al-Hanawi et al., 2020).

Pneumonia was the main clinical indicator of the COVID-19-related SARS-CoV-2 illness that allowed for case discovery. Asymptomatic infections and gastrointestinal symptoms were also indicated in current papers, particularly with regards to young children. According to observations, the incubation

period ranges from 0 to 24 days, with a mean of five days and an average of three days. The proportion of SARS-CoV-2-infected patients who do not exhibit any symptoms for the duration of the infection is still undetermined. In symptomatic patients or patients with symptoms, the illness usually manifests clinically in fewer than seven days and includes fever, coughing, nasal congestion, tiredness, and other upper respiratory tract infection-related symptoms. According to computed tomography (CT) scan results obtained at the time of admission, approximately 75% of patients get pneumonia and subsequent dyspnea and severe chest pains due to the infection. Usually, pneumonia strikes during the second or third week following a symptomatic infection. Prominent signs and symptoms of viral pneumonia include decreased oxygen saturation, blood gas deviations, abnormalities seen on chest X-rays and other imaging modalities, patchy consolidation, alveolar exudates, and interlobular involvement, which eventually indicate worsening. Proinflammatory cytokines and C-reactive protein, two inflammatory indicators, are high, and lymphopenia seems to be prevalent (Velavan & Meyer, 2020).

To stop the COVID-19 pandemic's rapid spread, which is a major medical and societal emergency, thus far unheard-of actions must be taken. People's understanding, attitudes, and behaviors regarding the illness have an effect on how closely they follow safety measures. If we compare the ways of life of the youth, students, and working class in this time of the pandemic, it is so much different from the life that we all used to live, where everyone is free to go wherever they want and even attend social gatherings. The "new normal" can be looked at as a law aiming to prevent people, mainly minors and senior citizens who are much more prone to being infected by the virus, from going out unless they are part of the front-line workforce, have an emergency, and acquire necessities. This time, businesses cannot fully operate, forcing small businesses and businesses that rely on the masses to survive to close due to bankruptcy, which eventually led to an increased unemployment rate. People are struggling to cope with the new normal. Some even do not understand that these new rules are being implemented for the greater good of COVID-19.

The rules related to COVID-19 keep changing, depending on the epidemiological report or incidence rate. In addition, the information about the nature of the virus also keeps changing. These changes may create confusion and stress as to what to do to prevent acquiring this disease, since until now there has been no concrete treatment regimen that will surely kill the virus and cure the disease. Thus, this study on determining the level of knowledge, attitude, and practices towards COVID-19 was conceptualized because these variables may contribute to the prevention and control of this pandemic disease condition, with a focus on the employees and higher education students of St. Dominic College of Asia as the research locale.

Literature Review

Knowledge towards COVID-19

In this research, knowledge was used to measure the information that the respondents already know or are aware of with regards to the following categories: preventive measures, causation, symptomatology, transmission, and management. Knowledge is even more important when it comes to COVID-19, as the wrong information can cost a life. Fake news may lead to confusion and chaos. It is imperative that people know the facts surrounding COVID-19, as it can cause wrong decisions that may lead to contracting the virus or, worse, death.

Unusual measures have been regulated to slow down the rapidly spreading COVID-19 pandemic in China. Individuals' adherence to control measures is influenced by their knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding COVID-19. The knowledge survey comprised 12 inquiries concerning the clinical attributes and avoidance of COVID-19. The correct general rating of the information poll was 90%. Programs for health education aimed at increasing awareness of COVID-19 can help Chinese citizens maintain appropriate behaviors and adopt idealistic mindsets (Zhong et al., 2020). In a similar study done in Sudan, the correct overall rate of the knowledge survey was 84.7%. Health education programs equipped with upgraded COVID-19 information are valuable for Sudan residents in disseminating knowledge

(Mousa et al., 2020). In terms of knowledge and practice, 92.7% and 79.5% of the dental experts had high or good scores, respectively. Years of practice and certifications were strongly correlated with high knowledge ratings ($p = 0.04$) and $p = 0.02$). They prepare their staff members to be sharp and adhere to the guidelines brought by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) in order to stop this pandemic from spreading (Kamate et al., 2020). In another study done among medical students in India, most participants had good knowledge. Even though the outcomes are positive, it is recommended that people keep on strengthening their knowledge of COVID-19 so that India can successfully fight against the virus (Maheshwari et al., 2020). A cross-sectional study was conducted by the Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College, Srinagar, in April 2020. A total of 1,358 respondents (89%) knew ways of transmission of the virus, and 602 (40%) felt that COVID-19 is a severe illness. The respondents demonstrated good knowledge regarding COVID-19 (Dkhar et al., 2020). Among 2,045 Bangladeshi respondents, 54.87% of respondents kept good knowledge (Haque et al., 2020). Residents' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) about the disease have an impact on how well they respond to control protocols. The results showed suitable practices, positive attitudes, and good knowledge of COVID-19, recommending that a community-based COVID-19 health education campaign be implemented in order to help contain the virus (Rugarabamu et al., 2020). The internet, social media (55.7%), and television (27.5%) were the main causes of the respondents' good knowledge (99.5%) on COVID-19 (Reuben et al., 2021).

Attitudes towards COVID-19

Attitude is used for the employees and students' confident responses with regards to the COVID-19 pandemic as to positive or negative attitude. It is important to have a positive attitude because what people think is what they attract. Being optimistic will help people see the good side in every situation instead of letting negativity drown them. It is not easy to be positive, especially with what everyone is experiencing right now because of the pandemic, but staying positive is necessary because it will help one focus on the things that need to be done during this COVID-19 pandemic.

An online example of Chinese inhabitants was effectively selected through the creators' organizations with occupants and famous media in Hubei, China. The members finished a self-created online KAP survey. Appraisals concerning residents' beliefs in winning their battle against COVID-19 and their recent outings wearing masks were among the methods used to assess their attitudes and behaviors regarding the virus. Most of the respondents (97.1%) knew that China could successfully fight against COVID-19. Many nations' capacity to respond to pandemics has been put to the test by COVID-19. Strict border controls and quarantine regulations have been implemented by numerous governments across the globe in an effort to suppress the spread of viruses. The National Capital Region (NCR) in the Philippines has been subjected to prolonged community quarantine. However, public cooperation is necessary for such initiatives to be effective. The participants are positive about the need for health education, the seriousness of COVID-19, and the need for stronger steps to contain the pandemic, but they are not as positive about the way the government is handling the situation. It was also demonstrated that the participants adhered to stringent guidelines in order to prevent the virus from spreading. The findings highlight the respondents' support for more stringent government controls to stop the COVID-19 virus from spreading, such as the reinstatement of an enhanced community quarantine in the NCR (Balibrea et al., 2020). Even though 61.8% of the participants have no confidence in Chinese doctors' present interference, only 29.0% would take COVID-19 vaccines when available. Programs for community-based health education are essential for fostering positive attitudes and putting into practice appropriate, misconception-free intervention techniques (Reuben et al., 2021).

Practices towards COVID-19

Practices are aimed at determining the actions of the respondents towards COVID-19 according to health protocols classified as good and poor practice. To fight the coronavirus, proper implementation of good practices towards COVID-19, such as ensuring physical distancing and frequent handwashing, should be done continuously. Protecting oneself against COVID-19 is still the best way to take action, according to the Department of Health (DOH).

Several countries have imposed harsh lockdowns, movement restrictions, or orders for groups to seek shelter in place in an effort to contain the COVID-19 pandemic. The cooperation and support of every member of society are essential to the effectiveness of the modifying measures. People's beliefs, behaviors, and information about the illness all play an important role in determining whether a society is willing to adopt health authorities' recommendations for behavioral changes. To enhance the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the people, it highlights the importance of consistent messages from government and health authorities as well as the necessity of specialized health education programs (Azlan et al., 2020). The presence of COVID-19 in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) is causing serious concerns regarding the spread of false information and the effectiveness of pandemic response and alertness in vulnerable health systems. Of the Filipino participants, 82.2% recognized hand washing as a protective measure against the infection, while only 32.4% and 40.6% recognized social distance and avoiding crowds, respectively. With 89.9% of participants, hand washing was the most widely used preventive measure against COVID-19. Those who were better informed about possible routes of transmission took more precautions. A need for directed health teaching as a responsible approach to COVID-19 in low-income backgrounds exists, and tactics must be contextually appropriate. It will be essential to know about KAPs in populations living in extreme poverty when specific guidelines for public health responses and interaction strategies are created for low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (Lau et al., 2020). Most of the participants (94.8%) were prepared to focus on the choice of remaining at home. The majority of participants (92%) made use of antiseptics or frequent hand washing. Health education programs equipped with upgraded COVID-19 information are valuable for Sudan residents in cultivating uplifting attitudes and disseminating knowledge relating to supportive practices (Mousa et al., 2020). In this examination, the Chinese inhabitants' KAP towards COVID-19 during the episode's quick ascent was explored. Practically the entirety of the members (98.0%) wore masks when going out in recent days. In numerous strategic relapse examinations, the COVID-19 knowledge score (OR: 0.75-0.90, $P < 0.001$) was essentially connected with a lower probability of preventive strategies towards COVID-19 (Zhong et al., 2020). The majority, i.e., 1,318 (87%), followed advisories and stated washing hands with soap and water regularly; 1,108 (73%) reported regularly wearing masks; 1,344 (89%) reported following lockdown regulations; and 1,306 (87%) reported maintaining social distancing. The respondents demonstrated sensible practices regarding COVID-19 (Dkhar et al., 2020).

All of the related literature will be utilized to compare and support our findings with what others have found regarding the same or similar questions, to determine what is already known about the topic, and to identify which parts of the study need further research. Those texts are good as a guide for the development of our study and for our research to be completed.

Significance of the Study

This study described the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of employees and higher education students of St. Dominic College of Asia towards COVID-19. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Educational Attainment

- 1.4 Occupation
2. What is the level of knowledge among St. Dominic College of Asia employees and higher education students towards COVID-19 in terms of:
 - 2.1 Preventive Measures
 - 2.2 Causation
 - 2.3 Symptomatology
 - 2.4 Transmission
 - 2.5 Management
3. What are the attitudes among St. Dominic College of Asia employees and higher education students towards COVID-19 in terms of:
 - 3.1 Positive Attitudes
 - 3.2 Negative Attitudes
4. What are the practices among St. Dominic College of Asia employees and higher education students towards COVID-19 in terms of:
 - 4.1 Good Practices
 - 4.2 Poor Practices
5. Is there a significant difference in the knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19 between the employees and higher education students of St. Dominic College of Asia?

Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant difference in the knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19 between the employees and higher education students of St. Dominic College of Asia.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design. Quantitative research helps discover what people think, how they react, and what they feel towards a particular research study. A descriptive-comparative method was used. This is a quantitative research design that will collect information from an individual respondent because it is more fixed with variables and methods used to determine the progress of data collection. The correct representation of the traits of individuals, circumstances, or groups, as well as the frequency at which particular phenomena occur, are characteristics of descriptive research (Polit & Beck, 2018). For this particular study, the researchers compared the employee and higher education student respondents of St. Dominic College of Asia as to their level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19.

Setting and Participants of the Study

This study was conducted through an online survey based within the institution of St. Dominic College of Asia, which involved employees and higher education students. There were nine employees and 51 higher education students who participated in the study, for a total of 60 participants.

Sampling Technique

The respondents of the study are the employees and higher education students of St. Dominic College of Asia in Bacoor, Cavite. The respondents were requested to participate in an online survey in order to explore their knowledge, attitude, and practice toward COVID-19. This research utilized convenience sampling. It is the process of choosing study participants who are the most easily accessible (Polit & Beck, 2018). This technique was considered due to restricted movements and transportation limitations being imposed by the national and local governments during a pandemic period. The researchers tried to connect with target respondents by using mobile phones and electronic mail for their inquiries and participation in the survey research.

Instrumentation

The researchers utilized a tool developed by Al-Hanawi et al. (2020) for their study in Saudi Arabia. The level of knowledge is measured by determining the percentage of correct answers in the questionnaire with the following qualitative interpretation:

80.21 – 100.00	Very High Level of Knowledge
60.41 – 80.20	High Level of Knowledge
40.61 – 60.40	Average Level of Knowledge
20.81 – 40.60	Low Level of Knowledge
1.00 – 20.80	Very Low Level of Knowledge

For respondents' attitudes: behavioral entries are categorized into two: positive attitude and negative attitude. Statements regarding attitude are all positively stated, agreeing to a statement is interpreted as *Positive*, disagreeing is interpreted *Negative*, while "not sure" is *neither*. To measure respondents' practices, compliance to health protocol is interpreted as *Good practice*. Non-compliance with health protocol is interpreted as *Bad practice*. The method of web-based survey tool was used in this research, in which Google Forms were sent via email, Facebook, and other social media accounts to facilitate distribution and retrieval.

The survey questionnaire used by the researchers was adopted from a similar study done in Saudi Arabia, according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. After the instrument is adopted, the adopting study can use the validity and reliability of the of the research studies that were performed on the instrument (Korb, 2012). Knowledge, attitudes, and practices were measured using the adopted KAP towards the COVID-19 Survey (Al-Hanawi et al., 2020). Al-Hanawi and colleagues reported reliability with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.70.

Data Collection

A series of steps in the protocol were followed by the researchers in order to obtain data. Upon approval of the proposed study, a request for permission was made to the school authorities. When all the permission and consent processes concerning the study were done, the distribution of the survey questionnaire through emails, Facebook, Messenger, and other social media accounts of the target respondents was done using Google Forms. In this form, the researchers listed all the necessary questions to acquire data concerning the respondents' knowledge, attitude, and practices towards COVID-19. This form was submitted to the Research Development Office for ethical review prior to its distribution. The respondents were requested to answer the given questionnaire through Google Forms according to their own time and availability. The questionnaire's distribution was done by sending a link to the target respondents through social media. After which, retrieval of the forms and collation of data were done.

Ethical Consideration

It is imperative in research to have ethical and legal considerations that the researchers must be aware of. The researchers informed the participants as to what kind of study they were conducting, the purpose of the study, and the methods that would be used in order to help them understand the implications of their participation in the study. An assurance of the anonymity and confidentiality of the data gathered was given. The consent of the participants was obtained. Moreover, the freedom to leave the study at any time without the researchers’ permission was communicated to the participants. The participants were encouraged to contact the researchers for any questions or clarifications about the study.

Limitations

There were only nine employees and 51 higher education students who participated in this study, out of 100 target participants. There were very few retrieved Google forms, probably because of the pandemic condition and/or poor online connectivity. The study is also limited within the institution of St. Dominic College of Asia and only covered the level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19 among employees and higher education students.

Data Analysis

To answer the research questions, the following statistical tools were utilized: For research question 1 as to profile characteristics, frequency and percentage distribution were used. For research questions 2, 3, and 4, frequency, percentage, and mean were used. To test the hypothesis of a significant difference between the respondents’ level of knowledge, attitude, and practices, a t-test was used. The 0.05 level of significance was utilized as the point of reference for accepting or rejecting the null hypothesis.

Results

Table 1 presents the profile characteristics of the respondents. Results revealed that most of employee respondents belonged to age group of 18 to 23 (n=4, 44.44%), were females (n=7, 77.78%), and with bachelor’s degree (n=5, 55.56%) while student respondents belonged to age group of 18 to 23 (n=35, 68.63%), were females (n=36, 70.59%), and are college undergraduates (n=33, 64.71%), coming from different courses and year levels.

Table 1. Profile Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Measure	Employees (n=9)		Students (n=51)	
		f	%	f	%
Age	18 to 23	4	44.44	35	68.63
	24 to 29	1	11.11	11	21.57
	30 to 34	0	0	2	3.92
	35 to 39	1	11.11	0	0
	40 to 44	1	11.11	2	3.92
	45 and above	2	22.22	1	1.96
Sex	Male	2	22.22	15	29.41
	Female	7	77.78	36	70.59
Educational Attainment	Graduated High School or Equivalent	2	22.22	10	19.61
	College undergraduate, no degree	0	0	33	64.71
	Bachelor’s degree	5	55.56	7	13.73
	Postgraduate degree	2	22.22	1	1.96

Table 2 presents the employees’ and students’ level of knowledge on COVID-19. Results showed that employee respondents have a very high level of knowledge regarding COVID-19, with an overall mean percentage of 82.08%. The highest mean percentage of 93.33% was obtained by knowledge on management, followed by knowledge on preventive measures with a mean percentage of 92.06%, both of which were interpreted as having a very high level of knowledge. Knowledge of transmission has the lowest mean percentage of 72.22%, interpreted as a high level of knowledge.

As for the students, it can be seen from the table that student respondents have a high level of knowledge regarding COVID-19, with an overall mean percentage of 77.33%. Knowledge of preventive measures has the highest mean percentage of 90.48%, followed by knowledge of management with a mean percentage of 85.88%, both of which were interpreted as having a very high level of knowledge. Knowledge of causation has the lowest mean percentage of 64.71%, interpreted as a high level of knowledge.

Table 2. Respondents’ Level of Knowledge towards COVID-19

Knowledge on COVID-19	Employees		Students	
	Mean Percentage	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean Percentage	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Preventive Measures	92.06%	Very High	90.48%	Very High
2. Causation	77.78%	High	64.71%	High
3. Symptomatology	75%	High	76.96%	High
4. Transmission	72.22%	High	68.63%	High
5. Management	93.33%	Very High	85.88%	Very High
Overall Mean Percentage	82.08%	Very High	77.33%	High

Table 3 presents the respondents’ attitudes towards COVID-19. Findings revealed that the employee respondents have positive attitudes towards COVID-19, with a mean percentage of 73.61%. Employee respondents’ attitudes toward health protocols and the importance of keeping their distance from others to avoid the spread of the virus both have a perfect score of 100% positive attitude. On the other hand, in terms of how the Philippine government is handling the health crisis, 44.44% of the employee respondents were not sure if the government is handling it well, while 33.33% disagreed, and only 22.22% agreed.

As for the student respondents, results revealed that they have positive attitudes towards COVID-19, with a mean percentage of 73.04 percent. All or 100% of the student respondents have a positive attitude toward the health protocols being followed, like the importance of keeping their distance from others to avoid the spread of the virus. On the other hand, in terms of whether the Philippine government is handling the health crisis very well, the majority of the student respondents (n = 35, 68.63%) disagreed, 13.73% agreed, and 17.65% were not sure.

Table 3. Respondents’ Attitudes towards COVID-19

Attitudes on COVID-19	Employees			Students		
	Positive Attitude (%)	Negative Attitude (%)	Neither (%)	Positive Attitude (%)	Negative Attitude (%)	Neither (%)
1. It is important to keep my distance from others, to avoid spreading COVID-19.	100%	0	0	100%	0	0
2. Washing hands is essential to protect myself from COVID-19.	100%	0	0	98.04%	1.96%	0
3. To protect myself from COVID-19 exposure, I should	100%	0	0	96.08%	1.96%	1.96%

stay home if I am sick, unless I am receiving medical care.						
4. Philippines' strict measures can help with the battle against COVID-19.	44.44%	22.22%	33.33%	80.39%	15.69%	3.92%
5. Compliance with the department of Health precautions will prevent the spread of COVID-19.	100%	0	0	92.16%	3.92%	3.92%
6. Do you agree that COVID-19 will be successfully controlled?	66.67%	11.11%	22.22%	56.86%	23.53%	19.61%
7. Do you have confidence that Philippines can win the battle against the COVID-19 virus?	55.56%	22.22%	22.22%	47.06%	13.72%	39.22%
8. The government of the Philippines is handling the COVID-19 health crisis very well.	22.22%	33.33%	44.44%	13.72%	68.63%	17.65%
Mean Percentage	73.61%	11.11%	15.28%	73.04%	16.18%	10.78%

Table 4 presents the employee respondents' practices towards COVID-19. Findings revealed that the employee respondents have good practices towards COVID-19, with a mean percentage of 98.15%. All (n = 9, 100%) employee respondents have a good practice of not attending any social event that involves a large number of people to prevent the spread of the virus. This is followed by the practice of going to crowded places; the majority of the employee respondents (n = 8, 88.88%) have been avoiding such practices, while 11.11% disagreed.

While for the student respondents' practices towards COVID-19, results showed that they have a mean percentage of 89.87% good practice. Student respondents have good practices for avoiding cultural behaviors such as shaking hands and wearing a face mask when leaving the house to prevent the spread of viruses (n = 50, 98.04%). On the other hand, 25.49% of the student respondents have bad habits by going to crowded places.

Table 4. Respondents' Practices towards COVID-19

Practices on COVID-19	Employees		Students	
	Good Practices (%)	Poor Practices (%)	Good Practices (%)	Poor Practices (%)
1. Going to a social event involving a large number of people	100%	0	80.39%	19.61%
2. Going to a crowded place	88.88%	11.11%	74.51%	25.49%
3. Avoiding cultural behaviors, such as shaking hands	100%	0	94.12%	5.88%
4. Practicing physical distancing	100%	0	98.04%	1.96%
5. Frequently washing hands with soap and water, for at least 40 seconds, especially after going to a public place, or after nose-blowing, coughing, or sneezing	100%	0	94.12%	5.88%
6. Wearing a face mask when leaving your home	100%	0	98.04%	1.96%
Mean Percentage	98.15%	1.85%	89.87%	10.13%

Table 5 presents the significant difference in the knowledge level of the employees and students. T-test results revealed a P value of 0.247 between the knowledge level of employees (M=82.08, SD=9.90) and students (M=77.33, SD=10.97), which therefore accepts the null hypothesis of no significant difference.

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Knowledge Level of the Employees and Students

	Mean	SD	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Employees	82.08	9.90	0.247	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Students	77.33	10.97			

Table 6 presents the significant difference in the attitudes of the employees and students. T-test results revealed a P value of 0.486 in the attitudes towards COVID-19 between the employees (M=73.61, SD=30.83) and students (M=73.04, SD=31.07), therefore accepting the null hypothesis of no significant difference.

Table 6. Significant Difference in the Attitudes of the Employees and Students

	Mean	SD	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Employees	73.61	30.83	0.486	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Students	73.04	31.07			

Table 7 presents the significant difference in the practices of the employees and students. T-test results revealed a significant difference, a P value of 0.047, between the employee (M=98.15, SD=4.54) and student (M=89.87, SD=9.95) respondents' practices towards COVID-19, therefore rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant difference.

Table 7. Significant Difference in the Practices of the Employees and Students

	Mean	SD	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Employees	98.15	4.54	0.047	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Students	89.87	9.95			

Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Based on the data presented, the employee respondents belonged to the age group of 18–23 years old, were female, and were bachelor's degree holders. While the student respondents belonged in the age group of 18–23 years old, were female, and were college undergraduates from different courses and year levels, in a similar study measuring the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of medical students in India, of the 354 participants, 50.3% were men and the remaining 49.7% were women; most of the men were between the ages of 21 and 23, while just 10% were above 24 (Maheshwari et al., 2020). Based on the results of this current study, 85% of the overall respondents that participated in this study are students, while 10% are non-academic employees, and only 5% are academic employees of the institution, which can be due to the fact that the study was conducted through a web-based survey and given the nature of today's education as online learning has increasingly become a part of the education system globally (Nambiar, 2020).

Respondent's Knowledge towards COVID-19

The level of knowledge of the respondents was measured through their correct answers in the survey questionnaire in the following categories: preventive measures, causation, symptomatology, transmission, and management. Findings revealed that both groups of respondents showed very high knowledge regarding preventive measures and management, while having a high level of knowledge regarding the causation, symptomatology, and transmission of the virus.

This implies that both employees and students are knowledgeable enough to follow minimum health protocols and protect themselves from acquiring the virus. A good example here is when all respondents answered that it is true that people should refrain from contacting their mouth, nose, or eyes with unwashed hands, as COVID-19 can be spread by rubbing a surface or object that has the virus attached to it and then touching those areas. These results could be probably due to the fact that the survey was done almost one year after the first community quarantine was implemented, in which there was sufficient time for the respondents to acquire knowledge and be aware of the facts related to COVID-19, may they be students or employees. During that one-year period of time, there was a massive information-dissemination campaign through multimedia, which they have seen and heard on television, radio, and the internet. Most of these campaign activities were initiated by the government, utilizing different simple or basic educational strategies, such as the use of cartoon drawings or caricatures. According to Balibrea et al. (2020), it is imperative to shed light on this information because the lack of awareness about the COVID-19 pandemic will merely make it more difficult for the authorities to disseminate basic facts about the virus. In addition, according to a study done among Tanzanian residents, considerable gaps in our understanding of diseases may lead to misunderstandings and weak control protocols (Rugarabamu et al., 2020).

Respondents' Attitudes towards COVID-19

The attitudes of the respondents were measured through their answers to the survey questionnaire. Results showed that both employee and student respondents have more positive attitudes towards COVID-19 than negative attitudes, specifically on keeping distance, washing hands, staying home, compliance with health precautions, and confidence in controlling the COVID-19 virus.

This means that both employees and students have an overall positive attitude towards the health protocols to be followed, even if some respondents disagreed on whether the crisis is being handled very well by the government. Their positive attitude regarding health protocols is probably because both employee and student respondents are eager to have this pandemic end as soon as possible, but they have doubts about whether they can rely on the government. Conversely, recent research conducted in Malaysia found that 89.9% of participants believed that the Malaysian government was doing a great job managing the COVID-19 situation (Azlan et al., 2020). Also, both employees and students were probably afraid of getting infected by the COVID-19 virus whenever they needed to go out of their house because they might put their family at risk as this virus has already done so much damage not only in the health sector but also in the education and economic sectors. Furthermore, in the study of Lee et al. (2021), most participants agreed that preventive measures, such as maintaining personal hygiene and avoiding close social interactions, are the most effective means of limiting the disease's transmission.

Respondents' Practices towards COVID-19

In this study, good and bad practices were used to determine the actions of the respondents towards COVID-19. The employee respondents have a higher mean percentage than the students when it comes to good practices, while the student respondents have a higher mean percentage than the employees when it comes to poor practices. However, both employee and student respondents have overall good practices that will help prevent acquiring and spreading the virus.

A similar study conducted in Saudi Arabia showed that most participants—91.9%—reported that they avoid contact with infected people by practicing social distance; 87.1% always wear masks when they go out; 83.9% stay away from crowded areas these days; and 77.4% routinely wash their hands with soap and water for no longer than 20 to 40 seconds (Begum, 2020). Furthermore, 89.9% of respondents to a recent survey conducted in the Philippines among low-income households indicated that hand washing was the most widely used preventive measure against COVID-19. Those who were better informed about possible routes of transmission took more precautionary steps (Lau et al., 2020).

Employees have a higher mean percentage of good practices than students, probably because they are the ones who often go outside their houses to work and interact with others, and therefore can be at risk of COVID-19. That is why employees always need to take preventive measures. Unlike the students who usually stay at home for online classes and are not allowed to go out of the house because of the curfew protocol, this is related to a recent study by Balibrea et al. (2020) in the Philippines that involved a sample of employed individuals in the National Capital Region. Of them, 80% paid more attention to their cleanliness, 82% used alcohol and other disinfectants, and 87% wore face masks when they were out in public.

Significant Difference in the Level of Knowledge of the Employees and Students

T-test results revealed no significant difference in the knowledge scores of the employees and students of St. Dominic College of Asia, which therefore retains the null hypothesis. In congruence with this finding, a similar study conducted by Haque et al. (2020) found that among the Bangladeshi population, their findings also revealed that students and employees showed no significant difference in their knowledge level regarding the virus. This can be due to the novelty of this virus and the impact it has had on the whole world, which led to information being shared across different platforms, from news to social media, reaching different demographic profiles and raising awareness. Employees are more inclined in watching the news for updates as they usually have the responsibilities of going to provide the needs of their family while ever since the first community quarantine last March 2020, news and updates about the virus has been widely spread through social media and according to a study done in Johannesburg by Ngoumandjoka (2012), it was revealed that students spend more time on the internet than studying and this is probably still the case now that students have been staying home ever since the said quarantine was implemented which dictates that no movement regardless of age and health status, no economic activity except essential sectors, and no face-to-face classes.

Significant Difference in the Attitudes of the Employees and Students

The t-test result revealed that there is no significant difference in the attitudes towards COVID-19 of the employees and students of St. Dominic College of Asia, which therefore retains the null hypothesis. This is probably because both employees and students have the same goal of protecting themselves and their families against the COVID-19 virus, which is the common enemy, and it is also possibly because they believe that having a positive attitude can lead to positive outcomes. Also, females tend to be more positive than males, and in this study, the majority of the respondents, both employees and students, are females. In congruence with this finding, a recent study conducted by Al Ahdab (2021) among Syrian residents also revealed no significant difference in the attitude of students and employees but in the attitude towards COVID-19 of males and females, where females showed a more positive outlook than males. Al Hanawi et al. (2020) also revealed that there is no significant difference in the attitude of employees and students but in the attitude towards COVID-19 of elderly and university students because college students are more aware of the situation during this pandemic, and both groups agreed that preventive measures are crucial to lower infection rates and stop the disease from spreading.

Significant Difference in the Practices of the Employees and Students

T-test results revealed a significant difference in the practice scores of the employees and students of St. Dominic College of Asia. This means employees have a higher mean percentage of carrying out the instilled health protocols than the students, probably because employees are the ones who are always exposed to the threat of the virus for the reason of going to work, whereas students stay at home for online classes. In effect, the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) even released workplace guidelines,

set to prevent the spread of COVID-19, where employees are required to follow precautionary measures, according to Trade Secretary Ramon Lopez and Labor Secretary Silvestre Bello III. They were released in May 2020. On the contrary to this finding, a similar study conducted by Mousa et al. (2020) revealed that employee respondents have a considerably higher risky behavior of poor practice due to the need to work daily for the sake of living. Employees can be at higher risk of performing poor practices compared to students; this is probably because they are the ones who necessarily need to leave the household. This group of people needs to maintain a good practice manner for the continuity of performing good practices. This also correlates with the study concluded in Syria (Al Ahdab, 2021), where participants performed good practices and documented poor practices were associated with younger respondents. In this regard, a group of younger people and/or students need to adhere and similarly express their good knowledge into good practice regarding safety measures.

Conclusion

It is therefore concluded that employees and higher education students of St. Dominic College of Asia have both a high level of knowledge, a positive attitude, and good practices towards COVID-19, regardless of their profile characteristics. There is a significant difference between employees and students in their practices of health protocols, but it has no effect on their level of knowledge or attitudes towards COVID-19. The employees have significantly better practices than the students.

The researchers recommend this research paper to the SDCA community to be used as a basis for learning materials for the people of the institution to further improve the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the students and the employees. This study is recommended to improve the weak points revealed, which are the following: respondents' knowledge about the causation of the virus, transmission, and symptomatology; respondents' attitude towards the government response; and practices of health protocols like avoiding attending social events, avoiding going to crowded places, avoiding shaking hands, and more frequent handwashing. It is essential to be able to observe the ability of the staff and students to handle this kind of battle against a virus that is invisible to the naked eye.

The researchers also recommend this to the SDCA administration as a baseline of the institution's KAP towards COVID-19 and as a basis for educational materials to further improve KAP levels. With the findings revealed in this study to be used to improve the knowledge of the community in preventing the spread of COVID-19, the researchers hope that this will help the people to realize the importance of having the right knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19, as limited knowledge, negative attitudes, and poor practices towards this disease might put oneself in danger, one might struggle to handle emergencies that may lead to situations least expected to happen, and it may cause a more serious situation because who is sick or infected with coronavirus cannot be known by just the mere appearance.

Future researchers may serve this study as a reference for future endeavors and a guide in broadening their knowledge about people's knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19. Future researchers are also recommended to do more studies about the knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19 to gather more information to improve and increase the reliability of the current data.

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